

Productivity of Coniferous Forests Evaluated by Remote Sensing and Field-Based Models

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Abstract

The inadequacy of Norway spruce monocultures in fulfilling ecosystem services, due to deteriorating health and consequent forest ecosystem collapses, has recently become a concerning issue for the forestry sector in Central Europe. This study investigates spruce forest productivity using in-situ field observations (DendroNetwork) and satellite remote sensing (RS) data in the Czech Republic during the past two decades. Tree growth index and MODIS net primary productivity were used to assess productivity at the national scale along an elevation gradient. The analyses of spatiotemporal variation in carbon dynamics indicate a decreasing trend in productivity in 51% and 80% (2, 800 km² and 4, 200 km²) of the spruce stands from the RS and in-situ data, respectively. The increasing trend is particularly evident in montane regions, where satellite data identified an elevation threshold around 700 m a.s.l. while in-situ data 900 m a.s.l. In these energy-limited montane areas, Norway spruce may benefit from increased temperatures and may remain relatively safe from drought stress. The decreasing trends detected by both approaches indicate deteriorating conditions for Norway spruce in lower elevations.

This study suggests that combining in-situ and RS data provides an efficient and robust way to estimate forest productivity at the national scale. The anticipated response of spruce forests associated with declines in productivity and growth in areas with low to moderate elevation points to the adverse effects of climate change by shifting the ecological optimum to higher elevations. We conclude that detailed mapping of forest response to changing environmental conditions is critical to support sustainable forest management and decision-making, ultimately reflecting the need to adopt adequate strategies to mitigate the impacts of climate change and related natural and anthropogenic disturbances.

Keywords: MODIS, DendroNetwork, Norway spruce, net primary productivity, tree growth, hotspots

1. Introduction

Studying the productivity and health of forests is imperative in light of the changing climate, as reliable spatiotemporal monitoring is required to address climate responses and societal demands (Piao et al., 2019). Forest ecosystems in central Europe, specifically in the Czech Republic, are characterized by high biodiversity determined by their unique geographical location and diverse geological and climatic history (Palmero-Iniesta et al., 2020; Wohlgemuth, 2015). Various soil types and topographical features support a wide range of plant and animal species, populations, and communities that occur on a relatively small scale (Chytrý, 2007). In this context, healthy forest ecosystems generate numerous ecosystem services for biota interactions, including i) providing habitats (Lindenmayer & Franklin, 2002), ii) enabling species migration through “green corridors” (Liira & Paal, 2013), iii) maintaining cool and moist conditions through transpiration and evapotranspiration processes (Bonan, 2008), and iv) providing ecosystem services that are crucial for society-nature interactions (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment Program, 2005). Moreover, forest ecosystems play an important role in providing biophysical and biogeochemical feedback to the climate systems (Liu et al., 2019). Maintaining healthy and productive forests has gradually become essential in the context of rapid climate change and its impact on forest ecosystems (Krejza et al., 2021).

Ongoing climate change associated with rising temperatures, potential evapotranspiration, and changing precipitation distributions may further accelerate the effects and frequency of drought periods (Crocetti et al., 2020; Hobeichi et al., 2021). The increased frequency and intensity of extreme climate events (Sellers & Ebi, 2018) namely heatwaves and droughts are estimated to become more frequent across all regions, implying further irreversible impacts on forests (Calvin et al., 2023; Salomón et al., 2022).

Forest ecosystems are currently facing disturbances at both the local and global scales (J. Tang et al., 2023; Waring & Running, 2007; Zhang et al., 2017). During the past 10 years, Norway spruce (NS)-dominated stands in the Czech Republic have been heavily damaged due to drought and consequent bark beetle infestation outbreaks (Bárta et al., 2021; Brázdil et al., 2022; Hlásny et al., 2021). There is indisputable evidence that suitable areas for growing and planting NS are shrinking (Buzek et al., 1986; Krejza et al., 2021; Kusbach et al., 2021). Works in related fields present further evidence for optimal conditions for NS in Western Carpathians (Macků and Kosová, 2020) or paleoecological observation data (Wiezik et al., 2020), indicating the specific habitat occurrences at the windward hill aspects, wetted valleys, and higher, cool mountain regions.

Here, we employ remote sensing (RS) techniques with a modern approach to in-situ data collection (DendroNetwork) to gain a unique perspective on NS forest productivity. Historically, many forest monitoring networks have utilized traditional growth measurements and often rely on manually recorded long-term data, such as national forest inventories and forest management plans (Zweifel et al., 2021). While these traditional methods provide reliable data, they cannot integrate automatic measurements and data collection with modeling to assess the current state of forest ecosystems (Zweifel et al., 2023). Continuous monitoring through dendrometers, which automatically record stem radius changes, offers an effective method for tracking the production function of forest ecosystems (Cocozza et al., 2016; Mencuccini et al., 2017). This approach is further enhanced when the system is designed for automatic data transmission and processing, resulting in up-to-date information. Combining satellite data with ground-based observations helps interpret point measurements through spatiotemporal context, identifies observational gaps, and provides up-to-date forest condition maps (Zweifel et al., 2023).

Earth-orbiting satellites, such as MODIS (Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer), Landsat (Land Remote Sensing Satellite), or SPOT (Satellite Pour l’Observation de la Terre) provide remote measurements of the Earth’s surface and atmosphere. MODIS data are advantageous because of their high temporal resolution (daily retrievals to 8-day and yearly composites), enabling time series and trend analysis of the

productivity data (Amantai et al., 2023; S. W. Running et al., 2004; X. Tang et al., 2015). The data spans a continuous and consistent 23-year time frame and provides valuable insights into the seasonal variation and interannual variability. A considerable number of studies have compared MODIS-derived net primary production (NPP) and gross primary production (GPP) to in-situ observations (Hasenauer et al., 2012; Neumann et al., 2015, 2016; Pan et al., 2006), although few works have specifically examined NS forests in Central Europe, particularly in the context of the ongoing susceptibility to climate-induced stress. Despite the relatively fragmented landscape in the Czech Republic, MODIS data have been used to adequately represent NS productivity due to their versatility, wide range of applications, and quick accessibility. This study represents an initial effort to combine RS data with continuous in-situ observations to illustrate the concurrent status of NS forest productivity at the national scale.

The objective is to assess and quantify the productivity of Czech NS forests using both satellite and in-situ data along an elevation gradient and compare the two approaches spatially over the past two decades (21 years) via inferential statistics. The enhanced spatial and temporal heterogeneity of NPP and tree growth index (TGI) is calculated and illustrated through specialized maps. To our knowledge, this is the first study that compares in-situ data with modern RS techniques to improve the current understanding of the underlying processes that drive the spatial heterogeneity of carbon uptake. In doing so, we aim to reduce the uncertainty in moderate-resolution estimations of forest productivity in diverse landscapes of the Czech Republic.

1. Methods

2.1. Study area

The research area encompasses forests dominated by NS (*Picea abies* (L.) H. Karst) in the Czech Republic, Central Europe (**Figure 1**). Approximately 34% of the Czech Republic is forested (~27 000 km²), where NS is the most abundant tree species with the highest economic importance. NS habitat has steadily decreased from 54.1% to 46.8% of forest land cover from 2001 to 2022 (MZe, 2023). NS naturally occurs in higher mountainous areas of the Czech Republic but has been largely planted in lower elevation areas (below 700 m a.s.l.), outside of its ecologically optimal niche. The annual precipitation gradient covering the distribution of NS is wide, between 400 and 1800 mm; the mean annual temperature varies between 1 and 11 °C (**Figure 1c**), with an increasing trend toward higher temperatures in the past two decades (**Figure 1c**; Zahradníček et al., 2021).

Figure 1. Natural distribution of Norway spruce in Europe (Skrøppa, 2003) (a.). Distribution of spruce-dominated forest stands in the Czech Republic (black dots represent DendroNetwork sites in spruce forests) (b.). Relationship between annual precipitation and mean annual temperature for spruce-dominated DendroNetwork sites for two observation periods (c.).

2.2. In-situ measurements of CO₂ fluxes

The in-situ measurements of forest carbon dynamics were based on the eddy covariance (EC) method at two ecosystem stations, with dominant NS forest growing under contrasting environmental conditions. EC data were used to evaluate satellite-based GPP estimates and the in-situ observations of tree growth on the basis of dendrometer measurements. We analyzed available time series datasets at two dominant spruce EC stations: Bílý Kříž, Moravian-Silesian Beskids Mountains (875 m a.s.l.) and Rájec, Bohemia-Moravian Highland (625 m a.s.l.). The former represents a characteristic montane forest stand located on a ridgeline of a major Czech mountain range, whereas the latter is situated in a low-elevation managed forest near the Moravian Karst nature protected area. Both stations operate under the national Czech Carbon Observation System (CzeCOS, <http://www.czecos.cz/>) and Bílý Kříž also belongs to the Integrated Carbon Observatory System (ICOS) as an ecosystem Class-II site, compiling continuous measurements of carbon uptake since 2005 (ICOS, 2024). Measurements at the Rájec site began in 2012. The fluxes were computed from the raw high-frequency using the software EddyPro® (version 6.2.0; LI-COR Biosciences, Lincoln, NE, USA) and further processed according to Reichstein et al. (2005), quality-checked and filtered using the U-star technique (Papale et al., 2006) to ensure reliable measurements. The post-processing was performed within the R package `openeddy` which follows the quality checking scheme described in (McGloin et al., 2018) and `ingrates` gap-filling and flux partitioning tool using the R package `REddyProc`

(Wutzler et al., 2018). The half-hourly fluxes were aggregated into an 8-day time step to match the MODIS products' time step.

DendroNetwork, an environmental research monitoring network (<http://dendronet.cz>), was used to capture in-situ tree growth phenology metrics of NS trees, including stem radius increments, and microclimate conditions. This technology captures high-resolution temporal data, providing valuable insights into tree growth patterns. DendroNetwork allows real-time, simultaneous data transfer and storage of environmental variables across different conditions and specific tree species. Ground-based growth data were collected from 30 DendroNetwork NS-dominated sites, covering a significant climate gradient with mean annual temperatures (2001–2022) ranging from 2.84 to 9.62 °C and mean annual precipitation ranging from 590 to 1 448 mm. The sites are distributed over an elevation gradient from 254 to 1 362 m a.s.l. Stem growth monitoring, based on changes in stem circumference measured by DRS26 band dendrometer (EMS Brno, the Czech Republic), was initiated in 2016 on seven NS plots and expanded to 30 plots by 2023, resulting in data collection durations ranging from two to eight years. The growth response of three to five trees at the codominant and dominant canopy layers was monitored per plot in 30-minute intervals and later aggregated into daily values.

2.3. Calculation of the Tree Growth model

Changes in circumference were recalculated as changes in stem radius. Dendrometer records include reversible water-related modifications and irreversible growth changes. To isolate irreversible growth, the "zero growth" concept was used (Zweifel et al., 2006). The annual stem radial increment (SRI) was determined as the difference between the maximum stem radius of the current year and that of the previous year or the first value for the first year of measurement. The start and end of the growing season were identified as the dates when 5% and 95% of the SRI, respectively, were achieved.

For a functional assessment of the relationship between climate and the SRI, the local vapor pressure deficit (VPD, kPa) was selected as a key driving variable in the model. The model was extrapolated using gridded meteorological data with a spatial resolution of 500 m based on meteorological observations from approximately 200 stations operated by the Czech Hydrometeorological Institute (Stepanek et al., 2013). Daily VPDs were calculated from the gridded climate data, including daily temperature and relative humidity. The annual VPD was determined as the average value per growing season that was derived from the SRI measurements. The modeled SRI for individual years (2001–2022; SRI_{year}) was compared with the growth pattern of the mean SRI within the baseline period (1981–2010; SRI_{long}) by computing a simple TGI (TGI_{year}) for a particular year:

$$TGI_{year} = \frac{SRI_{year}}{SRI_{long}}$$

2.4. Retrieval of remote sensing data

For the RS data analysis, time series of MODIS Terra MOD17A3HGF yearly NPP ver. 6.0 product (Running & Zhao, 2021) and MOD17A2H 8-day GPP ver. 6.0 (S. Running et al., 2021) were used. Both products are available at 500 m spatial resolution. The annual NPP is derived from the sum of all 8-day net photosynthesis products (MOD17A2H) from a given year. The NPP product was chosen as a robust proxy

for annual carbon allocation, closely mirroring the carbon uptake recorded through tree ring increments. Data and computations of long-term productivity trends for the study time frame (2001 to 2022) were facilitated through the geospatial platform Google Earth Engine ([Gorelick et al., 2017](#)).

To derive a representative spruce study mask, a spatially aligned MODIS grid with a resolution of 500 m has been produced over the study area, where NS occurrence is dominant, i.e., the areal proportion of NS to other species is greater than 50%. The generation of this “spruce grid” entailed the state-wide 5 m forest land cover classification (Forest Management Institute, 2019). Finally, an orthometric 30 m digital elevation model (NASA JPL, 2013) was used to assign an elevation class (interval every 300 m a.s.l.) and to extract elevation values corresponding to each spruce grid.

2.5. Hot spot and statistical analysis

To process annual TGI and MODIS NPP time series ranging from 2001 to 2022, the non-parametric trend estimator Theil-Sen’s slope method was used, allowing effective detection of long-term productivity trends across the study period (Sen, 1968; Theil, 1950). This was performed only on NS-dominated pixels masked by the “spruce grid” (Section 2.4). Regression analysis and inferential statistics, including Pearson’s coefficient of determination, confidence score (p-value), y-intercept and slope, were calculated in R ver. R 4.2.1 (R Core Team, 2021) analysis was implemented to identify areas where productivity values form significant spatial patterns, termed hot spots. The hot spot analysis was carried out using the Optimized Hot Spot Analysis tool (Spatial Statistics) in ArcGIS Pro vs. 3.2.2 Geographic Information System software (ESRI, 2023). The K-means clustering technique was employed to classify the extracted Sen’s slope scores of NPP and TGI. This step distinguished areas exhibiting significantly high or low productivity relative to their surroundings, described by the resulting proximity values and hot spot combinations.

3. Results

3.1. Agreement of satellite data with EC measurements

The in-situ GPP (based on the EC method) yielded a close agreement with the MODIS GPP (**Figure 2**). The analysis revealed strong correlations (Adj. $r^2 = 0.64$, RMSE = 17.1 g/m²/8-day for Bílý Kříž and Adj. $r^2 = 0.70$, RMSE = 11.7 g/m²/8-day for Rájec), indicating that the local GPP variations are consistent with the CO₂ flux measurements from the EC tower (**Figure 2**). Although the SRI growth periods were shorter than the photosynthesis-driven GPP (**Figure 2a, 2c**), we found a significant relationship ($p < 0.001$) between in-situ GPP and the daily rate of SRI for both sites (Adj. $r^2 = 0.42$ and 0.32 for Bílý Kříž and Rájec, respectively) (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2. Time series of in-situ estimated gross primary production (GPP) from the eddy covariance (EC) methods (black), satellite-based GPP derived from MODIS (blue), and stem radial increment (SRI_{rate}) from DendroNetwork (green) measured at two spruce-dominated, long-term ecosystem sites: Bílý Kříž (a.) and Rájec (c.). Correlations between in-situ GPP (EC method) and satellite-derived GPP and SRI_{rate} at Bílý Kříž (b.) and Rájec (d.). Significance level: *** $p < 0.001$.

3.2. Productivity trends from tree growth data

To assess the forest growth response at the national level, we developed a climate-growth relationship using VPD (the mean for the growing period) as a key variable. Most of the stem growth activity was observed from May 1 to October 31 (0.25 percentile start - DOY 121; 0.75 percentile end DOY). We were able to explain more than 80% (Adj. $r^2 = 0.89$) of the variability in the annual SRI (**Figure 3a**). The model's overall shape is unimodal, indicating an optimal VPD range for the SRI. Tree growth is less favorable both below and above this range, with the SRI peaking at approximately 0.4 kPa. As the VPD values approach 0.4 kPa, the SRI decreases sharply. Based on the nonlinear relationship between the annual SRI and VPD, and the VPD gradient within the Czech Republic shifting toward higher values, the country is divided into regions with positive and negative TGI trends (**Figure 4a**). This boundary occurs at an elevation of 880 m a.s.l. (**Figure 5**). Due to the shift toward higher temperatures and consequently higher VPDs, the regions where the optimal VPD (i.e., 0–0.4 kPa) has not yet been reached exhibit a positive trend. Conversely, there is an ongoing increase in VPD associated with a negative trend in TGI in areas where the VPD exceeds 0.4 kPa. At the most extreme sites with the highest VPD, a negative growth trend of 4% TGI was observed, indicating a potential decline in stem growth of up to 80% over 21 years ($\sim 4\,200\text{ km}^2$). Only 20% of the TGI observations exhibit a positive productivity trend ($\sim 1\,100\text{ km}^2$).

Figure 3. Relationship between average annual stem radial increment (SRI_{annual}), used here as a proxy for forest growth and productivity, and vapor pressure deficit (VPD - average during the growing season) measured at NS-dominated DendroNetwork sites ($n = 30$) between 2016 and 2023 (a.). The mean VPD for the baseline period 1981 to 2010 (b.), mean VPD for the period 2001 to 2022 (c.).

3.3. Productivity trend analysis of satellite data

The NPP Sen's slope of NS forest stands between 2001 and 2022 shows that most NS stands experienced losses or stagnation, except for the northwestern, northern and northeastern parts of the Czech Republic (**Figure 4b**). Unsurprisingly, these areas correspond to the major mountain regions, namely, the Ore Mountains, Giant Mountains, Jizera Mountains and Jeseníky Mountains. These are also the regions with the lowest observed VPD values during the observation period (0.2-0.4 kPa). According to **Figure 4b**, 51% of all NS forests exhibited a decreasing trend in productivity ($\sim 2\,800\text{ km}^2$) and 49% exhibited an increasing trend in productivity ($\sim 2\,600\text{ km}^2$).

Figure 4. Map of Sen's slope of the long-term trend of annual net primary production (NPP) derived from MODIS satellite data (a.) and Sen's slope of the long-term trend derived from the tree growth index (TGI) model (b.) at 500 m pixel resolution for the study period (2001–2022). The color theme from green to red represents the increasing and decreasing productivity trend, respectively.

Figure 5. Relationship between elevation and Sen's slope of net primary production (NPP) and the tree growth index (TGI) for the period 2001–2022 (a.). The significance level is given as *** $p < 0.001$. Box plots between NPP (b.), in-situ TGI (c.) spruce forest productivity across an elevation gradient. Lowercase letters indicate significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) estimated on the basis of the Tukey's ANOVA post hoc test.

3.4. Hot Spot Analysis: Spatial comparison of estimated productivity

Both approaches suggest that productivity in NS-dominated forests increases with elevation. We evaluated the correlation between MODIS NPP and in-situ TGI. First, regression analysis (**Figure 5**) revealed significant relationships between MODIS NPP and in-situ TGI with respect to elevation, with correlation coefficients of $r = 0.26$ and $r = 0.65$, respectively ($p < 0.01$). Compared with the NPP estimates, the TGI estimates showed a greater decrease in productivity with decreasing elevation. Furthermore, the threshold separating positive and negative TGI responses was determined at 880 m a.s.l., whereas the NPP threshold was 150 m lower.

Figure 6. Comparison of Sen's slope spatial patterns of MODIS net primary productivity (NPP) and in-situ tree growth index (TGI). The similarity value (a.) represents the degree of agreement between the two approaches in estimating spruce forest productivity. Dark to light green dots indicate areas of high to low agreement, respectively, between satellite and in-situ observations. The hot spot analysis (b.) shows the areas where the two estimated productivity approaches agree. The blue and light blue areas indicate where both MODIS NPP and TGI observations show increasing trends and the red and light red areas show decreasing trends.

Second, the HS analysis was used to identify areas of similar productivity trends. We found significant ($p < 0.05$) agreement between the satellite and in-situ data at both extremes, i.e., the sites with the highest growth limitations and the sites with higher growth rates. Areas of significantly high productivity constitute 11% of the NS-dominated regions and areas with significantly low productivity represent 12.4% of the analyzed area (Figure 6). In addition, transitional areas with slightly increasing and decreasing productivity account for 20.9% and 26.1%, respectively. Overall, 38.5% of all NS-dominated areas were found to have a decreasing productivity trend using a combination of analysis methods.

4. Discussion

For the first time, we introduced and compared two independent methods, in-situ observations and RS products, to assess the productivity trends in NS-dominated forests. By comparing the TGI based on stem increments, and NPP, which reflects the sequestered carbon by trees, we have enhanced the spatial and temporal resolution of forest productivity assessments compared with traditional approaches, which are solely based on in-situ forest inventories.

4.1. TGI model

Over the past decade, research has increasingly focused on factors limiting tree growth. VPD, a measure derived from air temperature and humidity, was identified as a critical determinant (Mirabel et al., 2023). Considering these findings, our objective was to develop a simple model based on a single parameter. While it is acknowledged that tree growth is influenced by more than just air temperature and humidity (e.g. Merganičová et al., 2019), the established model has proven to be sufficiently robust for evaluating forest growth at the country-wide scale. This acknowledgment highlights the capacity of our model to provide valuable insights into growth trends, despite the complex nature of ecosystem dynamics (McDowell et al., 2008).

The tree growth model effectively characterizes local habitat conditions, as VPD drives the spatial heterogeneity of the TGI. The resulting map (**Figure 4b**) shows compact patterns of TGI, reflecting the nature of the meteorological data and the distribution of ground observations across the study area. The observed elevation response in NS productivity and the influence of VPD on TGI aligns with the stress-response relationships reported by (Mirabel et al., 2023; Wen et al., 2024). The authors emphasize increasing seasonal dryness for sites located at lower elevations to become even drier. Furthermore, Mirabel et al. (2023) quantified tree growth responses in boreal forests by assessing tree-ring measurements with VPD, indicating that increased VPD has already inflicted broad-scale negative effects on tree growth, specifically in spruce species.

The TGI parameter, based on monitoring stem growth via a bottom-up approach, is particularly sensitive to drought episodes. Even in the initial stages of drought, there is a significant slowdown or complete cessation of stem growth (Krejza et al., 2021). Conversely, NPP, derived from a RS top-down approach that monitors the ecosystem at the canopy level, is more closely related to photosynthesis processes. The limitation of photosynthesis occurs at much higher levels of drought stress and might continue actively for a period beyond the activity of tree stem growth (Körner, 2015; Krejza et al., 2022; Peters et al., 2021). This distinction between the two processes indicates that stem growth cannot be directly inferred from the recently assimilated carbon, as it is more immediately and significantly affected by current water relationships than by the more buffered carbon budget (Zheng et al., 2023).

4.2. MODIS NPP

Although MODIS GPP and NPP products have been validated by previous studies (e.g., Heinsch et al., 2006; Turner et al., 2006; Wang et al., 2017), we evaluated them with EC measurements at the local scale at two flux tower sites with dominant NS species compositions but contrasting ages and canopy structures. Lower accuracies (Adj. $r^2 = 0.64$ and RMSE = 17.1 g/m²/8-day) were achieved at Bílý Kříž, an elevated hilly site, whereas better accuracy was achieved at Rájec (Adj. $r^2 = 0.71$ and RMSE = 11.7 g/m²/8-day), a site with typical productive NS monocultures growing in mid-elevation areas on flat terrain. Our accuracies are well in line with a validation study by (Wang et al., 2017), who compared the MOD17A2H GPP product at a 500 m spatial resolution with FLUXNET2015 data and concluded that MODIS underestimated flux-derived GPP at most sites yet reached the highest agreement ($r^2 = 0.71$) for the evergreen needleleaf forest biome. A

similar accuracy ($r^2 = 0.74$) was reported by (Montibeller et al., 2022) using 16 forest flux tower sites in Europe.

One limitation of the MODIS NPP/GPP algorithm is the simplistic land cover and biome identification. A “spruce grid” mask was applied to circumvent this limitation and achieve a more homogeneous forest environment. This step excluded recent disturbances, i.e., logging activities following bark beetle infestation, assuming only the presence of living trees during the analyzed period. Other limitations with forest representation can be addressed by implementing higher spatial resolution RS data; for example, [Senf & Seidl \(2021\)](#) successfully used Landsat data to depict declines in pan-European forests at 30 m spatial resolution, providing the avenue for future steps in this area.

4.3. Outlook for NS in a changing climate

Overall, our findings exhibit higher NPP than TGI trend estimations (**Figures 4a-b**), as the MODIS radiation use efficiency model tends to overestimate in forests with lower stand density (Neumann et al., 2016). The authors describe the dependence of MODIS NPP on representative VPD estimations, controlling the maximum radiation use efficiency, claiming that if VPD is underestimated, the NPP and GPP will be accordingly overestimated. The partial decoupling between the two processes, TGI and NPP, is also evidenced by a shift in the elevation at which the transition from a negative to a positive response occurs. This disconnection can be attributed to the differing sensitivities of these processes to limiting factors, primarily drought stress.

The correlations between NPP and TGI trends in our study resulted in moderate to strong relationships. This may be because the VPD was used as an input in both models, though it was employed under different assumptions and functional forms. The resulting NPP and TGI suggest increased NS forest productivity occurs under relatively high and moist conditions, i.e., areas with relatively low VPDs. Conversely, in warmer and drier regions below 800 m a.s.l., the TGI yields more reasonable estimates than NPP (**Figure 5b-c**). The discrepancy between the modeled estimates likely lies in the resolution of the meteorological input data, from which the VPD is derived, i.e., $0.5^\circ \times 0.66^\circ$ GMAO/NASA (MODIS NPP) and 500 m gridded data interpolated from observations by Czech Hydrometeorological Institute.

Furthermore, we showed that NS exhibited an elevation-dependent productivity trend, with a decline at lower elevations and an increase at higher altitudes. [Kašpar et al. \(2024\)](#) and [Tumajer et al. \(2017\)](#) reported that NS stands in Central European forests demonstrate divergent growth trajectories associated with elevation-based patterns from 1990 to 2014. Their results also revealed an expected prevalence of positive NS growth trends above 800 m a.s.l., though this threshold was identified already at 580 m a.s.l. Other studies have shown that in addition to elevation, environmental gradients, such as CO₂ fertilization and climate warming also impact forest productivity patterns, particularly at relatively high latitudes ([Forkel et al., 2016](#); [Lin et al., 2020](#)). Specifically, extended growing seasons and reduced temperatures in high elevations may offset the drought-induced stress on NS.

The negative impact of NS monocultures on Czech forest management has been well documented since the 1980s and should not be dismissed when planning future forest policies ([Buzek et al., 1986](#)). Through the knowledge gained in this study, several key points are recommended for forest management to address: (i) identify areas of high and low productivity, (ii) adjust forest planting practices to site-specific conditions, and (iii) avoid planting NS monocultures below 800 m a.s.l. and prioritize the planting of mixed forests to improve forest resilience in the future.

Given our in-situ observations, the future climate trajectories outlined in the IPCC report (Calvin et al., 2023), and the reviewed literature, we emphasize a rising concern surrounding stability, even the very existence of NS stands at low to moderate elevations (200 to 800 m a.s.l.) of the Czech Republic (Krejza et al., 2021; Kusbach et al., 2021; Machová et al., 2024; Salomón et al., 2022).

5. Conclusions

This work compares MODIS satellite data with in-situ observations from the DendroNetwork to perform a comprehensive assessment of spruce forest productivity and carbon dynamics across the Czech Republic. Strong correlations between MODIS NPP and in-situ measurements were found. Pronounced spatial patterns are discernible in the major montane regions in the north and northeast of the country, with NS-dominated stands exhibiting a positive productivity trend above 800 m a.s.l. This finding is consistent with both approaches. Conversely, low productivity at lower elevations, plateaus, and exposed landscape structures is likely related to site-specific conditions, droughts, and impractical forest management, such as NS monocultures.

We highlight the observation that the two fundamentally different approaches exhibit significant spatial patterns and statistical agreement. This finding opens new possibilities for integrating these methods to enhance the accuracy of productivity estimates, such as calibrating satellite data via DendroNetwork observations into a single powerful model.

Further research will enhance current observational methods by employing high-resolution datasets to create a national-level product that would be meaningful and actionable for forest management practices, recently released product of Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, namely, seasonal productivity. This 10 m pan-European dataset has been available since 2017 and addresses scale discrepancies between RS and DendroNetwork data. Considering the current exacerbating spruce forest conditions, we recognize this topic as a key priority for future scientific research and forest management practices.

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Appendix

Appendix 1. Relationship between Sen slope satellite MODIS net primary production (NPP) and in-situ TGI for the period 2001-2022. Dark dots represent 1000 m spatial aggregation, gray dots represent 500 m spatial aggregation (i.e. per pixel comparison).